

Assessment of Availability and Utilisation of Biology Resources for Secondary Schools in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed availability and utilisation of Biology resources for secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The descriptive research design of the evaluative type was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all 1,851 Biology teachers in all the public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted of 180 biology teachers drawn from 90 public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria using multistage sampling procedure. Inventory on Biology Materials (IBM) was used for collecting the data for the study. The face and content validity of the instrument were ensured by presenting the instruments to specialist in the fields of Tests and Measurement, and Science Education. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through the test re-test method which yielded reliability co-efficient value of 0.78. The data collected through the instruments was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the result revealed that most of the schools have functional laboratories but do not meet the recommended standard of at least 2 periods per week for practical work in Biology. Also, it was revealed that most of the schools do not have all the recommended instructional materials while most of the teachers did not utilize the available instructional materials. It was further revealed that availability and utilization of instructional materials for teaching

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Biology do not differ in southwest Nigeria. It was recommended among others that the educational stakeholders should place greater emphasis on the provision of equipments and instructional materials needed for Biology teaching and practical work.

Keywords: Assessment, Availability, Utilisation, Biology Resources,

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Introduction

Biology is a significant science subject and an obligation for further learning of a number of science related expert courses like medicine, agriculture, pharmacy among others. Biology is also a vital science subject option for many students to please registration requirement at the Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE). In contemporary Nigeria, more emphasis is positioned on science and technological development. As a result, students are being encouraged to take up science-related subjects. Today, Biology saturates literally every field of human endeavour, and plays an essential role in educational advancement. This is seen in all the technologically advanced countries of the world today, as a result of scientific investigations.

Biology is a captivating subject that ranges from microscopic cellular molecules to the biosphere, surrounding the earth surface and its living organisms (Olayinka, 2016). Biology offers contents in the training of students who want to study medicine, nursing, pharmacy, forestry, fisheries and so on. Requirement of a credit pass and above in Biology is needed for science related discipline. Most of the senior secondary school students choose Biology as an option in the West African Senior School Certificate Examinations (WASSCE) or National Examination Council's Senior School Certificate Examinations (NECO SSCE). Even, for some students, Biology is a subject of first choice because they find it to be a stimulating subject being a subject that is more related to nature.

Biology laboratory is very vital in curriculum implementation as laboratory seems to be the most appropriate place to obtain the right scientific services and attitudes. In the laboratory, the student is given the opportunity to progress and practice the processes of science such as observations, communication, formulation of hypotheses, experimentation and classification. Though numerous schools in Nigeria have a general laboratory. The single laboratory is used for all sciences (Olayinka, 2016) such situation where a single ill-equipped room is being used as laboratory for all sciences would certainly be highly insufficient and inappropriate for efficient learning since each science subject has its own distinctiveness. Some of the schools that have distinct laboratory cannot boast of having suitable and modern equipment. laboratory apparatus are very vital to ease learning and improve the curriculum coverage in Biology.

There is a shortage in facilities in the laboratories as this could generate a gap in Biology curriculum implementation which may contribute to students' poor academic performance in Biology at the secondary school level. The researcher perceived that the few schools who can brag of a good laboratory do not appropriately utilized it for the improved performance of students. Laboratory attendants are conspicuously absent in most secondary schools. What they have are what they call substitutes (Ajayi, 2008). The so-called substitutes may not be efficient because it is difficult for one to give what he/she doesn't have. The resulting effect on students is that many of them cannot have access to most of the laboratory apparatus and not exposed to practical work in Biology which is a core area in the curriculum.

The teaching and learning instruction of Biology just like any other science subject demands energetic students contribution involving the use of material resources. However, the researcher perceived that crucial material resources are incompetently provided in both rural and urban secondary schools in Nigeria. The significance of instructional materials to the fruitful implementation of Biology curriculum cannot be overstressed. This is because the use of instructional materials is a sine qua non for effective behavioural change in learners (Jimoh, 2009). It seems that when the students are given the opportunity to learn through more senses than one, they can learn faster and easier.

The indispensability of instructional materials for teaching cannot be overstressed. Students seem to attain greater learning as evidence in attainment of cognitive and psychomotor services when instructional materials are used for instructional purpose. Therefore, one cannot distinct the influence of instructional materials availability from the performance of school students in Biology. In spite of the importance placed on the worth of instructional materials in Biology teaching and learning process, it seems that most teachers still finds it hard to make use of instructional materials in the classroom.

The researchers also perceived that the instructional materials that should improve Biology teaching which will accumulate into better academic performance appear not provided as required. The needed steps and efforts required from Biology teachers as ingredients for teaching efficiency appear to be lacking and this could also add to poor implementation of the Biology curriculum. The sufficiency of instructional materials as well as their effective utilization has been a matter of serious concern to educators. The utilization of instructional materials in Biology could bring about productive learning outcomes since it stimulates and motivates students.

Based on the foregoing, this study assessed availability and utilisation of Biology resources for secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

- i. the level of availability of functional Biology laboratories in secondary schools;
- ii. the depth of practical work done in Biology in schools;
- iii. the level of availability of instructional materials;
- iv. how Biology teachers utilize the available instructional materials for teaching and learning of Biology;
- v. the difference in the availability of instructional materials for teaching Biology among the three states; and
- vi. the difference in the utilization of instructional materials for teaching Biology among the three states.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study:

1. What is the level of availability of functional Biology laboratories in secondary schools?
2. What is the level of practical activities done in Biology curriculum in the schools?
3. What is the level of availability of instructional materials for teaching Biology in the schools?
4. How often do the Biology teachers utilize the available instructional materials for teaching and learning Biology?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were generated for this study

1. There is no significant difference in the availability of instructional materials for teaching Biology among the selected three states in Southwest, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the utilization of instructional materials for teaching Biology among the selected three states in Southwest, Nigeria.

Methodology

The descriptive research design of the evaluative type was adopted for the study. The design was chosen to present the evaluative data to be collected for the study. The design allowed information to be obtained from a representative sample of the population in the actual situation as they exist. The population of the study comprised all 1,851 Biology teachers in all the public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The states in South West of

Nigeria are Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo and Ekiti. The total number of Biology teachers in public secondary school in Lagos State is 329, Ogun State is 308, Oyo State is 417, Osun State is 274, Ondo State is 257 while Ekiti State is 266 (**Source:** States Ministries of Education, 2019).

The sample for the study consisted of 180 biology teachers drawn from 90 public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria using multistage sampling procedure. In stage one, three out of six states in the Southwest, Nigeria, were selected through random sampling technique by balloting. The second stage involved the selection of six Local Government areas from each of the selected states using simple random sampling technique. In stage three, five public secondary schools were selected from each of the sampled Local Government areas using simple random sampling technique. In stage four, two Biology teachers were selected from each of the schools using purposive sampling technique. In all, 180 teachers were drawn from 90 secondary schools in 18 Local Government of 3 states in South West, Nigeria.

Inventory on Biology Materials (IBM) was used for collecting the data for the study. It consisted of section A and B. Section A consisted of bio-data of the respondents while section B contained 30 items which checked the availability and utilization of instructional materials for Biology teaching. The availability aspect of the inventory has three options as follows: Adequate, Inadequate and Not available. Schools with the recommended numbers of instructional materials are classified as adequate while schools without the recommended numbers are classified as inadequate and schools without any of the materials are classified as not available. The utilization aspect of the inventory also has three options as follows: Frequently Used (FU), Hardly Used (HU) and Not Used (NU).

The face and content validity of the instrument were ensured by presenting the instruments to specialist in the fields of Tests and Measurement, and Science Education. To ensure face validity of the instruments, the experts helped to determine the face value of the appropriateness of the instruments. To ensure content validity, the experts checked the items and ascertained that the items represented the variable specified in the research questions. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through the test re-test method. In doing this, a study was carried out in 5 secondary schools outside the sampled schools. The instrument was administered on 10 biology teachers and within a period of two weeks, the instrument was re-administered on the same respondents. The data collected on the two tests were correlated using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation statistics which yielded reliability co-efficient value of 0.78 which was considered high enough to make the instruments reliable.

The data collected through the instruments was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The evaluation questions were answered using frequency counts, percentages, means and standard deviation. All the hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistics at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Question 1: What is the level of availability of functional Biology laboratories in secondary schools?

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Analysis of Availability of functional Biology Laboratories

Level of Availability	Available	Not Available	Total
No of Schools	59	31	90
Percentage	65.6	34.4	100

Table 1 showed availability of functional Biology laboratories in secondary schools. Out of the 90 secondary schools, 59 secondary schools representing 65.6% had functional Biology laboratory while 31 secondary schools representing 34.4% do not have a Biology laboratory. It means that the level of availability of functional Biology laboratories was moderate. Figure i further showed the availability of Biology laboratories in secondary school.

Figure i: Bar Chart Showing Availability of Functional Biology Laboratories

The graph showed that 65.6% of the secondary schools had functional Biology laboratory while 34.4% of the secondary schools do not have a Biology laboratory. Therefore the level of availability of functional Biology laboratories in secondary school is moderate.

Question 2: What is the depth of practical work done in Biology in secondary schools?

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage Analysis of Practical Work in Biology Per Week

Period	None	1	2	3	Total
No of School	28	51	11	-	90
Percentage	31.1	56.7	12.2	0	100

Table 2 showed that 28 (31.1%) of the schools sampled had no period for teaching of practical work in Biology while 51 (56.7%) of the schools sampled do practical only once per week and 11 (12.2%) of the schools sampled do practical work twice per week. Hence, most of the schools do not meet the recommended standard of at least 2 periods per week for practical work in Biology given by Federal Ministry of Education (2013). It follows that the period for practical work in Biology was low

Research Question 3: What is the level of availability of instructional materials for teaching Biology?

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage analysis of availability of instructional materials

S/N	Topics	Adequate		Inadequate		Not Available	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
1.	Biology Laboratory	59	65.56	0	0.00	31	34.44

2.	Refrigerator	12	13.33	0	0.00	78	86.67
3.	Charts	38	42.22	33	36.67	19	21.11
4.	Beakers	53	58.89	28	31.11	9	10.00
5.	Burners	49	54.44	29	32.22	12	13.33
6.	Gas Cylinders	51	56.67	21	23.33	18	20.00
7.	Microscopes	39	43.33	37	41.11	14	15.56
8.	Dissecting Boards	58	64.44	19	21.11	13	14.44
9.	Hand lens	52	57.78	26	28.89	12	13.33
10.	Mammalian bones	64	71.11	17	18.89	9	10.00
11.	Jars	54	60.00	22	24.44	14	15.56
12.	Conical flasks	56	62.22	24	26.67	10	11.11
13.	Stop watch	50	55.56	31	34.44	9	10.00
14.	Spring Balance	64	71.11	0	0.00	26	28.89
15.	Test tubes	47	52.22	29	32.22	14	15.56
16.	Pipettes	41	45.56	37	41.11	12	13.33
17.	Thermometer	38	42.22	41	45.56	11	12.22
18.	Tripod and Clamp stand	43	47.78	36	40.00	11	12.22
19.	Weighting balance	51	56.67	0	0.00	39	43.33
20.	Metre rules	37	41.11	23	25.56	30	33.33
21.	Retort stand	42	46.67	21	23.33	27	30.00
22.	Hydrochloric acid	38	42.22	0	0.00	52	57.78
23.	Other acids	51	56.67	17	18.89	22	24.44
24.	Other Bases	48	53.33	19	21.11	23	25.56
25.	Disposable hand gloves	21	23.33	26	28.89	43	47.78
26.	Textbooks	57	63.33	33	36.67	0	0.00
27.	Methylated water	39	43.33	22	24.44	29	32.22
28.	Iodine solution 2	40	44.44	27	30.00	23	25.56
29.	Benedict solution	29	32.22	42	46.67	19	21.11
30.	Fehling Solution	33	36.67	37	41.11	20	22.22
	Average	45	50.15	23	25.81	22	24.04

Table 3 showed the level of availability of instructional materials during teaching in Biology. It was revealed that the schools who had adequate Biology laboratory, refrigerator, charts, beakers, burners, gas cylinders and microscopes were 65.56%, 13.33%, 42.22%, 58.89%, 54.44%, 56.67% and 43.33% respectively. It also showed that the school who had adequate dissecting boards, hand lens, mammalian bones, jars, conical flasks, stop watch, spring balance and test tubes were 64.44%, 57.78%, 71.11%, 60.00%, 62.22%, 55.56%, 71.11% and 52.22% respectively.

The study further showed that the schools who had adequate pipettes, thermometer, tripod and clamp stand, weighting balance, metre rules, retort stand, hydrochloric acid, other acids and other bases were 45.46%, 42.22%, 47.78%, 56.67%, 41.11%, 46.67%, 42.22%, 56.67%, and 53.33% respectively. It was showed that the school who had adequate disposable hand gloves, textbooks, methylated water, iodine solution 2, benedict solution and fehling solution were 23.33%, 63.33%, 43.33%, 44.44%, 32.22% and 36.67% respectively.

Schools with the recommended numbers of instructional materials are classified as adequate while schools without the recommended numbers are classified as inadequate and schools without any are classified as not available. The table revealed that less than 75% of

the sampled schools have adequate instructional materials. The table also revealed that the highest adequately available materials are the spring balance and mammalian bones with 71.11% of the sampled schools having both in their laboratory. The least adequately available material is refrigerator with only 13.3% of the sampled schools it in their laboratory.

The table showed that 50.15% of the sampled schools had adequate availability of instructional materials which implies that the level of availability of instructional materials for teaching Biology is moderate.

Research Question 4: How often do the Biology teachers utilize the available instructional materials for teaching and learning of Biology?

Table 4: Frequency and Percentage analysis of utilization of instructional materials

S/N	Topics	Frequently Used		Hardly Used		Not Used	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
1.	Biology Laboratory	47	52.22	12	13.33	31	34.44
2.	Refrigerator	12	13.33	0	0.00	78	86.67
3.	Charts	27	30.00	44	48.89	19	21.11
4.	Beakers	31	34.44	39	43.33	20	22.22
5.	Burners	13	14.44	42	46.67	35	38.89
6.	Gas Cylinders	11	12.22	56	62.22	23	25.56
7.	Microscopes	18	20.00	54	60.00	18	20.00
8.	Dissecting Boards	17	18.89	50	55.56	23	25.56
9.	Hand lens	21	23.33	51	56.67	18	20.00
10.	Mammalian bones	41	45.56	39	43.33	10	11.11
11.	Jars	29	32.22	39	43.33	22	24.44
12.	Conical flasks	29	32.22	40	44.44	21	23.33
13.	Stop watch	12	13.33	59	65.56	19	21.11
14.	Spring Balance	23	25.56	35	38.89	32	35.56
15.	Test tubes	22	24.44	39	43.33	29	32.22
16.	Pipettes	19	21.11	43	47.78	28	31.11
17.	Thermometer	27	30.00	38	42.22	25	27.78
18.	Tripod and Clamp stand	23	25.56	42	46.67	25	27.78
19.	Weighting balance	18	20.00	28	31.11	44	48.89
20.	Metre rules	39	43.33	19	21.11	32	35.56
21.	Retort stand	19	21.11	25	27.78	46	51.11
22.	Hydrochloric acid	8	8.89	19	21.11	63	70.00
23.	Other acids	13	14.44	38	42.22	39	43.33
24.	Other Bases	15	16.67	34	37.78	41	45.56
25.	Disposable hand gloves	5	5.56	17	18.89	68	75.56
26.	Textbooks	78	87.64	11	12.36	0	0.00
27.	Methylated water	44	48.89	11	12.22	35	38.89
28.	Iodine solution 2	28	31.11	21	23.33	41	45.56
29.	Benedict solution	21	23.33	32	35.56	37	41.11
30.	Fehling Solution	19	21.11	42	46.67	29	32.22
	Average	24	27.03	34	37.75	32	35.22

Table 4 showed the utilization of the available instructional materials during teaching in Biology. It showed that the schools who frequently use Biology laboratory, refrigerator,

charts, beakers, burners, gas cylinders and microscopes were 52.22%, 13.33%, 30.00%, 34.44%, 14.44%, 22.22% and 20.00% respectively. It also showed that the school who frequently use dissecting boards, hand lens, mammalian bones, jars, conical flasks, stop watch, spring balance and test tubes were 18.89%, 23.33%, 45.56%, 32.22%, 32.22%, 13.33%, 25.56% and 24.44% respectively.

The study further showed that the schools who frequently use pipettes, thermometer, tripod and clamp stand, weighting balance, metre rules, retort stand, hydrochloric acid, other acids and other bases were 21.11%, 30.00%, 25.56%, 20.00%, 43.33%, 21.11%, 8.89%, 14.44%, and 16.67% respectively. It showed that the school who had adequate disposable hand gloves, textbooks, methylated water, iodine solution 2, benedict solution and fehling solution were 5.56%, 87.64%, 48.89%, 31.11%, 23.33% and 21.11% respectively.

The table showed that textbooks are the only materials fully utilized by over 50% of the sampled schools as other materials are not fully utilized by over 50% of the sampled schools. The table also showed that the highest fully utilized material by the sampled schools is textbooks with 87.64% of the sampled schools fully utilized it. The least fully utilized material is disposable hand gloves with only 5.56% of the sampled schools fully utilized it.

The table above showed that only 27.03% of the sampled schools frequently utilize the instructional materials which implies that the level of utilization of instructional materials is low.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the availability of instructional materials for teaching Biology among the selected three states in Southwest, Nigeria.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance for availability of instructional materials for teaching Biology among the three states

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12.200	2	6.100	0.534	.588
Within Groups	994.700	87	11.433		
Total	1006.900	89			

$P > 0.05$

The result presented in table 5 showed that F-cal value of 0.534 is not significant because the P value (0.588) > 0.05 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in the availability of instructional materials for teaching Biology among the three states.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the utilization of instructional materials for teaching Biology among the selected three states in Southwest, Nigeria.

Table 6: Analysis of Variance for utilization of instructional materials for teaching Biology among the three states

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.756	2	.878	0.055	.947
Within Groups	1392.200	87	16.002		
Total	1393.956	89			

$P > 0.05$

The result presented in table 6 showed that F-cal value of 0.055 is not significant because the P value (0.947) > 0.05 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is

not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in the utilization of instructional materials for teaching Biology among the three states.

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that over half of the secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria had functional Biology laboratories but most of the schools do not meet the recommended standard of at least 2 periods per week for practical work in Biology, so the depth of practical work in Biology was low. This implies that there were not enough periods in the school time-table to cater for practical aspect of Biology. The only available periods cater for the theoretical aspect and this could justify the reason why most Biology teachers use the periods for Biology theories alone. Okebukola and Akinbola (2008) and Nwagbo (2008) concluded that one of the major challenges militating against the implementation of the Biology curriculum is lack of practical teaching of Biology. The above findings about not giving Biology enough time are true because almost all the topics in Biology subject require practical. After teaching the theory part of it; then there is need to take the students to the laboratory to do the practical. But you find out that in most times, there is no time to teach the students the practical aspect of Biology.

The result of this study also showed that most of the schools do not have all the instructional materials as they all fall below the recommendation standard by Federal Ministry of Education (2014). This implies that instructional materials were not adequate for the implementation of national Biology curriculum. Instructional materials seem not to be adequate in most of our secondary schools, thereby affecting the achievement of the content of the national Biology curriculum. Most Biology teachers have been teaching Biology without the necessary instructional materials. This present finding is in consonance with the findings of Folorunso (2004) who concluded that there is lack of adequate and appropriate instructional resources for effective teaching of Biology in schools.

The study also showed that most of the teachers did not utilize the available instructional materials as recommended by Federal Ministry of Education (2014) for the implementation of the Biology curriculum. This implies that the available instructional materials are lowly utilized by Biology teachers. This finding agreed with the conclusion of Okebukola (2004) who concluded that the poor state of laboratory facilities and inadequate use of instructional materials has constituted a cog in the wheel of adequate implementation of the curriculum. Ibitoye and Fape (2007) concluded that the poor achievement in Biology was traced to inadequate usage of instructional resources for Biology teaching and learning.

The study also showed that there was no significant difference in the availability and utilization of instructional materials for teaching Biology among the three states. This implies that the level of availability and level of utilization of instructional materials in public secondary schools of the sampled three states are not different. The finding is in consonance with the submission of Folorunso (2004) who also found out that there were no differences in the availability and utilization of instructional materials in most of the public schools.

Conclusion

Sequel to the findings of this study, it was concluded that most of the schools have functional laboratories but do not meet the recommended standard of at least 2 periods per week for practical work in Biology. Most of the schools do not have all the recommended instructional materials while most of the teachers did not utilize the available instructional materials. It was further concluded that availability and utilization of instructional materials for teaching Biology do not differ in southwest Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The educational stakeholders should place greater emphasis on the provision of equipments and instructional materials needed for Biology teaching and practical work in Biology
2. Biology teachers should always use the instructional materials while teaching so as to ensure adequate implementation of the national Biology curriculum.
3. School administrators should ensure that only qualified teachers are recruited to teach Biology in senior secondary schools. Qualified and sufficient numbers of dedicated teachers are needed to teach the contents of the curriculum.

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